

ADHERENCE TO HAEMODIALYSIS REGIMEN AND ASSOCIATED FACTORS AMONG CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE PATIENTS IN NNAMDI AZIKIWE UNIVERSITY TEACHING HOSPITAL, NNEWI, ANAMBRA STATE, NIGERIA”

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Abstract: Background: Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) globally has become an increasing public health concern which necessitates management with haemodialysis (HD). Adherence to prescribed haemodialysis session aids to improve patients' health outcomes and reduce mortality rate. However, poor adherence to haemodialysis among CKD patients has been a major problem. It equally constitute a public health threat which deserve holistic attention in Anambra State. **Aim:** The study determined the adherence to haemodialysis regimen and associated factors among chronic kidney disease patients in Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital (NAUTH) Nnewi, Anambra State, Nigeria. **Materials and Methods:** A descriptive cross-sectional survey design was adopted for the study, sample size was 127 and Purposive sampling technique and census method were used for the study. The instrument for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire and data obtained were analysed using Microsoft excel, Chi-square for hypothesis testing and IBM statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 29. **Results:** It revealed that most CKD patient have poor adherence to prescribed haemodialysis session (65.40%), due to lack of finance (96.06%), haemodialysis is expensive and unaffordable, (100%), lack of social support (85.80%), age (56.62%), occupation (55.89%). **Conclusion:** Chronic Kidney Disease is one of the public health concerns in Anambra State which result in increasing number of patients who require haemodialysis, poor quality of life, depression, financial strain, high morbidity, high hospitalization and death. Patients' adherence to prescribed HD session was poor The major associated factors to adherence are high cost of haemodialysis, lack of finance, lack of social support, age and occupation. Therefore, hospital management and government should subsidising the cost of HD and expand the health insurance scheme to fully accommodate the management of CKD to improve adherence thereby promoting patients' quality of life and reduce mortality rate.

INTRODUCTION

Globally, chronic kidney disease (CKD) has become a public health issue affecting people of all ages, social classes and especially people suffering diabetes mellitus and hypertension (Kovesdy, 2021 and Jager, *et al.*, 2019). Chronic kidney disease has become an increasing global public health concern because of the high morbidity, mortality and increasing number of patients who require renal replacement therapy (RRT) which include haemodialysis (HD) and kidney transplant (Naalweh, *et al.*, 2017). Globally, Chronic kidney disease is one of the most common non-communicable disease with significant mortality rate worldwide (Global Burden of Disease Chronic Kidney Disease Collaboration, 2017). Chronic kidney disease also known as chronic renal disease that is irreversible characterized by gradual loss of kidney function over time (National kidney Foundation, 2023). Chronic kidney disease can be defined as the progressive and an irreversible impairment or permanent loss of kidney function occurring gradually over three months or more as a result of permanent damage to the kidney structures (Alikari, *et al.*, 2018). The major contributory or causative factors to chronic kidney disease (CKD) according to National kidney foundation, (2023) include diabetes mellitus, hypertension, glomeruonephritis and autoimmune diseases. Chronic kidney disease is more prevalent in older individuals, women, racial minorities, and in people suffering diabetes mellitus and hypertension. Chronic kidney disease represents

an especially large burden in low and middle income countries, which are least equipped to deal with its consequences (Global Burden of Disease, 2023; International Society of Nephrology, 2023 and Kovesdy, *et al.*, 2021). According to Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) estimated that about 37 million American adults have chronic kidney disease and millions of others are at increased risk (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2023).

Haemodialysis is the main and preferred treatment modality for chronic kidney disease that can increase the life expectancy and enhances quality of life in chronic kidney disease patients (Mukakarangwa, Chironda, Bhengu, and Katende, 2018; Nagasawa, Tachi, Sugita and Esaki, 2018). Haemodialysis is the most widely used type of dialysis and a method that is used to achieve the extra corporeal removal of waste products such as creatinine, urea and excess water from the blood when the kidneys are in a state of renal failure (Li, *et al.*, 2020). Successful management of chronic kidney disease patients with haemodialysis is anchored on the life-time adherence of patients to the prescribed treatment regimen (Naderifar, Zagheri, Ilkhani, Akbarizadeh and Ghaljaei, 2018).

Adherence to haemodialysis is referred to as doing or undergoing two to three sessions of dialysis in a week with each session lasting four to five hours without skipping or missing scheduled dialysis session or rescheduling prescribed dialysis session which is very important to achieve optimal treatment (Duong, Olszyna, Nguyen and Malaws, 2015; Wang, *et*

al., 2018). Non-adherence to the prescribed haemodialysis regimen is a major concern that affects patient outcomes, including survival and can result to life-threatening consequences which is associated with increased morbidity, mortality, cost and burden on the health care system (Alhawery, Aljaroudi, Almatar, Alqudaimi, and Alsayyari, 2019; Ok and Kutlu, 2020). Recent studies in Nigeria have not demonstrated a change in trend as factors responsible for this ranges from poor health financing, unaffordability due to out-of-pocket payment and grossly inadequate HD centers in the country (Oluyombo, *et al.*, 2016). Another major problem that contributes to failure in the management of chronic kidney disease with haemodialysis regimen is poor therapy adherence by patients with chronic kidney disease (Naalweh, *et al.*, 2017). The alarming rise in the incidence of CKD in Nigeria is likely to continue if patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD) lack knowledge of this disease, its management, and practices to support effective self-management (Okoro, *et al.*, 2020).

Associated factors that can affect adherence to the prescribed haemodialysis regimen with CKD patients include patients related factors (age, gender, religion, financial status, educational level, family/social support, co-morbidity status), therapy related factors (cost, duration, side effects and psychological effect of the haemodialysis) and institutional related factors (location of dialysis centers, health information knowledge, cost of haemodialysis, inadequate dialysis machine, poor maintenance of dialysis machine, lack of specialised medical personnel) (Alikari, *et al.* 2018; Chironda and Bhengu,

2016; Kilonzo, Kyalo and Shisoka, 2021; Mugi, Githemo and Osongo, 2021; Mukakaragwa, *et al.*, 2018; Naalweh, *et al.*, 2017; United states Renal Data system, 2020). In Nigeria, several studies have shown that approximately 20 million Nigerians are living with CKD and about 80% of these patients do not sustain treatment beyond 3 months, resulting in repeated hospitalization, poor quality of life, high morbidity, and premature deaths (Arogundade, *et al.*, 2021; World Kidney Day, 2022). Therefore, this study aimed to determine the adherence to haemodialysis regimen and associated factors among chronic kidney disease patients in Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching, Hospital Nnewi, Anambra State, Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A cross-sectional descriptive survey adopted for the study. The area of study was Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching, Hospital Nnewi, Anambra State, Nigeria. Purposive sampling technique and census method were used for the study. The sample size was 127. The instrument for data collection was a self-developed questionnaire which was validated by three experts; two nephrologists and a measurement and evaluation specialist. A split-half test was used to test for reliability. Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital Health Research Ethics Committee Nnewi, Anambra State. Ethical consideration were duly observed. The data was computed in IBM SPSS and internal consistency was analyzed using Cronbach Alpha which yielded 0.85. Data Collection lasted for 3 months. Data obtained

were analyzed using, Microsoft excel, descriptive statistics and Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 29. Research questions were answered using frequency and

percentages. Chi-square was used to test hypothesis. Level of significance in hypothesis testing were set at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

Table 1: Showing the Socio-demographic Variables of CKD patients in Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching, Hospital Newi, Anambra State. n = 127

Variables	Classes	Frequency (%)
Age (Years)	9-24	10(7.90)
	25-44	33(25.98)
	45-64	62(48.80)
	65&Above	22(17.32)
Mean Age	49.65±16.73	
Gender	Male	89(70.08)
	Female	38(29.92)
Marital Status	Married	86(67.72)
	Single	30(23.62)
	Separated/ Divorced	11(8.66)
Level of Education	No formal education	6(4.72)
	Primary	13(10.24)
	Secondary	50(39.37)
	Tertiary	58(45.67)
Religion	Christian	119(93.70)
	Traditionalist	7(5.51)
	Muslim	1(0.79)
Occupation	Self-Employed	55(43.31)
	Employed	38(29.92)
	Unemployed	26(20.48)
	Retired	8(6.30)
Any Presence of other chronic illness?	Yes	90(70.87)
	No	34(26.77)
	Not sure	3(2.36)
If yes specify (n=90)	Diabetes	52(57.78)
	Hypertension	32(35.56)

Cancer	3(3.33)
HIV/AIDS	2(2.22)
Hepatitis C	1(1.11)

At what Stage does CKD was diagnosed? Stage 1	20(15.75)
Stage 2	19(14.96)
Stage 3	23(18.11)
Stage 4	13(10.23)
Stage 5	52(40.95)
Total	127(100)

Table 1 above, 48.80% of the respondents were within the age of 45-64 years, 70.08% were male, 67.72% were married, 45.67% had tertiary education, 93.70% were Christians, 43.31% were

self-employed, (70.87%) had other chronic illness), (53.30%) had diabetes, and (40.95%) were diagnosed at Stage 5.

Table 2: showing the Adherence to prescribed Haemodialysis session among CKD patients in Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching, Hospital Nnewi, Anambra State. n= 127

Variables	Frequency (%)	
	YES	NO
Do you believe taking haemodialysis as prescribed can improve your health and prevent complication?	124(97.6)	3(2.4)
How many sessions of haemodialysis do doctors prescribed for you weekly?		
Once	15(11.8)	
2 times	33(26.0)	
3 times	79(62.2)	
Do you come or adhere to haemodialysis regularly as prescribed	44(34.6)	83(65.4)
How many times in a week do you come for haemodialysis		
Once	45(35.4)	

Twice	71(55.9)
Three	11(8.7)

Have you ever missed any session of haemodialysis as prescribed 98(77.2) 29(22.8)

What cause the missed session of haemodialysis?

No money	82(64.6)
Cost of Haemodialysis	4(3.1)
Side of haemodialysis	7(5.5)
Long distance	2(1.6)
Lack of family support	3(2.4)
Have not missed	29(22.8)

How do you pay for haemodialysis sessions?

Personal business/ salary	69(54.3)
Family contribution	50(39.4)
Fundraising	8(6.3)
NHIS Insurance	0(0.0)

How many years have you been on haemodialysis

Less than 1 year	93(73.2)
1 to 2 years	30(23.6)
More than 2 years	4(3.2)

How many hours you spent for each haemodialysis session

4 hours	126(99.2)
More than 4hours	1(0.8)
3 hours	0(0.0)

Overall Result: Good Adherence 44(34.6), Poor Adherence 83(65.4)

Table 2 above, (97.6%) of the respondents believed that HD can improve their health, (62.2%) were prescribed HD three sessions weekly, (65.4%) do not come as prescribed, (55.9%) come twice weekly, (77.2%) have

missed one or two HD sessions weekly, (64.6%) said no money caused the missed HD session, (54.3%) pay for HD session from personal business /salary, (73.2%) have been on HD for

less than 1 year, and (99.2%) spent 4 hours for each HD session.

Most 79(62.2%) were prescribed 3 times HD session weekly, among 79 respondents on 3 times HD, only 11(13.9%) adhere to prescribed HD session, 53(67.1%) come twice, 15(19.0%) come once. Among 33(26.0%) prescribed twice

HD session weekly, only 18(54.5%) adhere while 15(45.5%) come once not adhere. All the respondents 15(11.8%) on once HD session weekly adhere as prescribed. Overall result of the adherence showed that 83(65.4%) had poor adherence while 44(34.6%) had good adherence to prescribed HD session.

Table 3: showing Patient Related Factors Associated with Adherence to HD Regimen among CKD patients in Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching, Hospital Nnewi, Anambra State.

Items	Highly (4)	Moderate ly (3)	Slightly (2)	Not All (1)	At Mean s Score	Remark
My age	26(20.4)	40(31.50)	6(4.72)	55(43.31)	2.3	Accepted
My occupation	14(11.0)	36(28.35)	21(16.54)	56(44.09)	2.1	Accepted
My religion	2(1.57)	22(17.32)	12(9.45)	91(71.65)	1.5	Rejected
Being male or female	5(3.94)	14(11.02)	6(4.72)	102(78.7)	1.4	Rejected
Level of education	11(8.66)	15(11.81)	14(11.02)	87(68.51)	1.6	Rejected
Lack of finance	112(88.19)	8(6.30)	2(1.57)	4(3.94)	3.8	Accepted
Lack of social support	77(60.6)	32(25.20)	4(3.15)	14(11.03)	3.4	Accepted
Preference of other alternative treatment	18(14.1)	26(20.47)	13(10.24)	70(55.12)	1.9	Rejected
Forgetfulness	7(5.51)	15(11.81)	9(7.09)	96(75.59)	1.5	Rejected
Haemodialysis is	101(79.30)	20(15.75)	6(4.72)	0(0.00)	3.7	Accepted

expensive and unaffordable

I don't believe that I have CKD

9(7.09)

9(7.09)

9(7.09)

100(78.7)

1.4

Rejected

Mean Score >2.0 (items accepted), ≤2.0 (items rejected), Overall Mean Scores = 2.2

Table 3 shows the results were summarized with mean scores and remarks indicating whether each patient related factor was accepted or rejected based on a threshold mean score of 2.0.

Majority of the respondents accepted and agreed with these items (lack of finance, haemodialysis is expensive and unaffordable,

lack of social support, age and occupation) as patient related factors highly associated with the adherence to prescribed HD session.

Table 4: Test of Association between the patients' adherence to prescribed HD session and patients' age, gender, marital status , level of education, religion and occupation.n=127

Variables	Adherence to haemodialysis		χ^2	P-value
	Good(44)	poor (83)		
Age (years)			2.82	0.42
≤24	3(30.0)	7(70.0)		
25-44	10(30.3)	23(69.7)		
45-64	20(32.3)	42(67.7)		
≥65	11(50.0)	11(50.0)		
Gender			0.56	0.46
Male	29(32.6)	60(67.4)		
Female	15(39.5)	23(60.5)		
Marital status			0.80	0.67
Single	9(30.0)	21(70.0)		
Married	32(37.2)	54(62.8)		
Separated/ Divorced	3(27.3)	8(72.7)		
Level of education			1.94	0.59
No formal education	1(16.7)	5(83.3)		
Primary	3(23.1)	10(76.9)		
Secondary	18(36.0)	32(64.0)		
Tertiary	22(37.9)	36(62.1)		
Religion			0.67	0.72
Christian	42(35.3)	77(64.7)		
Muslim	0(0.0)	1(100.0)		

Traditional Occupation	2(28.6)	5(71.4)		
Employed	19(50.0)	19(50.0)	7.91	0.04*
self-employed	13(23.6)	42(76.4)		
unemployed	8(30.8)	18(69.2)		
Retired	4(50.0)	4(50.0)		

KEY= *Significant $p < 0.05$

Table 4 show that the age group 65 years and above were the most adherent to prescribed HD session (50.0%), 24years and below was the least adherent (30.0%), though age was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). The female was more adherent to HD than the males (39.5%:32.6%) though gender is not statistically significant. The married were the most adherent (37.2%) though it is not statistically significant. Tertiary level of education were more adherent (37.9%) however the difference is not significant. Christians were more adherent (35.3%) to HD than others though not significant. The employed and the retired were the most adherent (50.0%:50%) to HD and it is statistically significant ($P < 0.05$).

There was no significant association between the patients' adherence to prescribed HD session and patients' age, gender, marital status, level of education, and religion ($p > 0.05$).

There was significant association the patients' adherence to prescribed HD session and patients' occupation ($p < 0.05$)

DISCUSSION

This study revealed that a total of 127 Chronic Kidney Disease Patients on haemodialysis session in Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital, Nnewi, Anambra State participated in the study. The findings on the Adherence to

Haemodialysis Regimen among Chronic Kidney Disease Patients was 65.40%. The results on patient's adherence to prescribed haemodialysis session showed that most (65.40%) had poor adherence. This is consistent with previous findings on the level of adherence to haemodialysis by Mohamedi and Mosha, (2022); Ehwareme and Awhim,(2021); Kilonzo, Kyalo and Shisoka, 2021. Again, study done by Chege, Githemo and Onsongo, (2022) showed that level of adherence to haemodialysis treatment was moderate 53 percent. The findings showed despite opening new hemodialysis centers to increase availability and accessibility of haemodialysis services, adherence still remains a major challenge among patients. Studies have shown that the level of HD adherence among CKD patients on maintenance HD has been found to be low with approximately half of the patients being non-compliant (Chiroda and Bhengu, 2016; Kilonzo, Kyalo and Shisoka, 2021).

The study done by Mukakarangwa, *et al.* (2018) revealed low adherence in 49% of CKD participants. The findings are consistent with findings from Geldine, Bhengu, and Manwere, 2017 that 50% of patients on haemodialysis not adhering to their dialysis regimen. Similarly, thirty-nine percent of the study population

missed their dialysis sessions at least once. This is also similar to the findings of Duong, *et al.* 2015 and Al-Khattabi who revealed 42% and 44% of CKD patients that missed their dialysis sessions, respectively (Al-khattabi, 2017).

The finding of this study showed that following patients related factors; lack of finance, haemodialysis is expensive and unaffordable and lack of social support significantly influence adherence to haemodialysis regimen. This is consistent with previous findings by Ehwareme and Awhim, (2021) in Benin City Edo state, Nigeria identified financial constraints, lack of transportation, forgetfulness, and long waiting times were factors affecting adherence. Again, Akpor, Yakubu and Akpor, (2023) in Kwara state identified high cost of HD treatment as a .barriers to adherence. Meremo, Ngilangwa, and Mwashambwa, (2017) in Tanzanian study pointed out that high cost of HD treatment is a major challenge to adherence to HD among CKD patients. Kustimah, *et al.*, (2019) pointed out that the low economic status of CKD patients undergoing HD greatly impacts on their adherence. Furthermore Chironda and Bhengu, 2016 in Rwanda, the high cost of haemodialysis treatment was mentioned by most of the participants to affect attendance of haemodialysis sessions because most of the time, missed dialysis sessions were related to financial constraints. Low socio-economic status has been reported among CKD patients and where the majority of the CKD patients were unemployed by (Chironda, *et al.*, 2016). Ramitiliana, *et al.*, (2016) a study done in Greece reported that the high cost of HD treatment has been a major barrier to

compliance to HD. Patients have to pay from their pockets for treatment which is difficult because majority of the patient's population are low income earners. This makes it impossible for patients to attend all HD sessions result to non-compliance. Alexopoulou, *et al.*, (2016) study done in Greece revealed that social support influence HD compliance. Lack of adequate support is a hindrance to adherence with HD treatment. Patients with inadequate assistance were probably more likely to miss or shorten the duration of HD session (Alikari, *et al.*, 2018). Nakao, *et al.*,(2016). A Brazilian study pointed out that, family support is an important factor in ensuring compliance with dialysis regimen by individuals with CKD.

This study showed that the age, gender, marital status, level of education, religion were not significantly associated with the patients' adherence to prescribed HD regimen. This is contrary with Mukakarangwa, *et al.*, (2018) in Rwanda revealed that age was statistically significantly associated with adherence to haemodialysis. Alhamad, *et al.* (2023) in Saudi Arabia revealed that gender, education level, Social support and transportation were significantly influenced adherence. Adequate family and social support were associated with better adherence.

Again the finding of this study show that the age group 65 years and above were most adherent to prescribed HD session and 24years and below were the least adherent. This is consistent with the work done by Chironda and Bhengu, (2016) revealed that young patients are less compliant to HD unlike older patients. Younger patients and those diagnosed having chronic illnesses

are less adherent. Higher adherence behaviour is found in older patients. Again, American Kidney Foundation Resources stated that, over 50% of young patients shorten their dialysis sessions than the older patients (AKF, 2018). Young patients regard themselves physically healthier than older patients leading to missing HD sessions (Som, *et al.*, (2017), Sumji, Ruggajo, and Moledina, 2020). A systematic review done in Rwanda emphasized that older patients were more compliant to HD than younger patients. This has been associated with aged persons being better organized in their life and can accommodate any charge that may arise unlike young persons who regard themselves safe to adverse health outcomes (Chironda and Bhengu, 2016). Also, elderly persons have a greater concern with death, thus follow their treatment regimen to avoid it (Nakao, *et al.*, 2016). This contradicts the finding by Ehwareme and Awhim (2021) that respondents 18 to 30 years are nine times more likely to adhere than those who are greater than 60 years.

Again the finding of this study show that the female was more adherent to HD than the males though the majority of CKD participants were males rather than females and gender is not statistically significant. The married were the most adherent than single. Tertiary level of education were more adherent. Christians were more adherent to HD than others. The employed and the retired were the most adherent to HD and it is statistically significant. This consistent with the finding of Chironda and Bhengu, (2016) revealed that being male is consistently associated with non-adherence. This

consistent with the finding by Ehwareme and Awhim (2021) that males are less likely to adhere than females. Married patients are twice more likely to adhere than those who are not, while respondents who are not educated are less likely to adhere than those with college/university certificate. The results are consistent with findings of G´erard, Augustin, and Rogeretal, (2016) who revealed that the majority of CKD participants were males rather than females. This is similar to the study findings by Chironda, *et al.*, (2016) who revealed that the males were representing 57% and 43% were females. Contrary to these findings are the findings of Burkhalter, *et al.*, (2014) that showed the predominance of females (65%). Duong, *et al.*, (2015) study the males represented 47%. Gender was not associated with adherence to haemodialysis. However, this is in contrary to study done by Naalweh, *et al.*, (2017) where male patients had significantly higher overall adherence scores than females.

Again, the findings of this study contradict the work done by Mukakarangwa, *et al.*, (2018) revealed that religion was significantly associated with adherence to haemodialysis. This also contradict with a prospective study conducted by Freire de Medeiros *et al.* 2017 that established religiosity to be associated with adherence to dialysis.

Again the findings of this study was consistent with the work done by Mukakarangwa, *et al.*, (2018) Ibrahim, *et al.*, (2015); Nakao, *et al.*, (2016) varying levels of education were not significantly associated with the level of adherence to haemodialysis among CKD

population. This shows that CKD affects both educated and non-educated people meaning that knowledge alone is not a predictor of adherence to haemodialysis (Ibrahim, *et al.*, 2015; Nakao,*et al.*, 2016). However, a decreased level of education can contribute to reduced levels of understanding leading to non-adherence and poor level of following medical instructions in favor of CKD treatment (Chironda and Bhengu, 2016). On the contrary, increased level of education facilitates capturing and conveyance of information regarding concerns of the disease CKD as well as importance of haemodialysis treatment.

Alikari, *et al.*, (2018) a study conducted in Greece on adherence to therapeutic regime in adult patient undergoing haemodialysis revealed that the higher the education level, the higher the compliance. Furthermore, Acar, *et al.*, (2018) noted that factors such as age, cultural structure, cost of treatment, side effects associated with treatment, feelings that patients have about the treatment, social support, resources, and illness perception affect the adherence and outcomes of haemodialysis among CKD patients.

IMPLICATION OF FINDINGS

Findings of this study revealed that the patients' adherence to the prescribed HD sessions was poor. Therefore, there is need for patients to understand the important of attending HD as recommended which can improve their health and prevent complications as well reduce mortality rate.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that the overall adherence to prescribed HD sessions was relatively poor,

due to financial constraints, unaffordable cost of HD, cost of haemodialysis is not subsidized, side effect, stay longer time during haemodialysis.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Government and hospital should subsidising the cost of HD and more enlightenment campaigns will help improve adherence to treatment
2. The patients and their families should be equipped with adequate information concerning the nature of the CKD and the support systems required through counseling programmes. These would create awareness, thus promoting more support and enhancing compliancy.
3. The patients should be encouraged to continue with their income generating activities even when they are on haemodialysis treatment in order to have sufficient income to support their families economically and pay for their treatments.

LIMITATIONS AND FURTHER RESEARCH

Geographical barrier, time constraint, respondents' unpredictable behavior and lack of funds were limitations faced by the researcher during the course of the study.

It is highly recommended that similar study on the same subject should be replicated involving the other tertiary health care facilities

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COVER LETTER FOR SUBMISSION OF MANUSCRIPT

Date: 22nd SEPTEMBER, 2025

I am enclosing here with a manuscript of a research article entitled “**ADHERENCE TO HAEMODIALYSIS REGIMEN AND ASSOCIATED FACTORS AMONG CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE PATIENTS IN NNAMDI AZIKIWE UNIVERSITY TEACHING HOSPITAL, NNEWI , ANAMBRA STATE, NIGERIA**” for publication in **your esteemed Journal Advanced Journal of , Nursing and clinical practice**

The paper should be of interest to readers in the areas of Nephrology, public/community health, general nursing, medicine, and related fields. The Corresponding author of this manuscript is Onwuasoanya Adaku Nonyelum and the authors with their affiliations are mentioned below

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With the submission of this manuscript I would like to undertake that:

- All authors of this research paper have directly participated in the planning, execution, or analysis, manuscript writing of this study.
- All authors of this paper have read and approved the final version submitted;
- The contents of this manuscript have not been copyrighted or published previously;
- The contents of this manuscript are not now under consideration for publication elsewhere and there is no conflict of interest;

Please address all correspondence concerning this manuscript to me at **atuegwuadaku@gmail.com**

Thank you for your consideration of this manuscript.

Sincerely,

Adaku Nonyelum Onwuasoanya